

Analysis of Classroom Infrastructure Facilities on Student Motivation at SMK Negeri 2 Karanganyar

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Abstract:

Learning motivation is a person's psychological condition that encourages learning activities. Students' learning motivation can be influenced by several factors, including the condition of the infrastructure available in schools and classrooms. The purpose of this study was to see the condition of infrastructure facilities whether there is an influence on student learning motivation in class XI RPL at SMK Negeri 2 Karanganyar. The research method uses quantitative methods by collecting interview and questionnaire data with a sample of 30 students in class XI RPL. The results of the study show the influence of infrastructure on learning motivation as evidenced by the results of the correlation test $r_{count} > r_{table}$ value, namely $0.748 > 0.361$ with a significance level of 5% in the range of 0.60 - 0.79 which is categorized as "strong". Each instrument is tested for reliability which results in a value of $0.80 > 0.361$ which means reliable. While the percentage of each instrument gets 75.1% for infrastructure facilities and 74.9% for motivation. In other words, school infrastructure facilities have an effect on the motivation of class XI students in learning activities.

Keywords: *Classroom Infrastructure, Learning Motivation, Quantitative*

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Introduction

Education is an important foundation for training quality human resources. Education cannot be separated from learning and teaching activities. Every human person has the opportunity to achieve proper education to develop and develop abilities within themselves and improve education for related institutions. Based on the definition in the National Education System Law No.20 of 2003 Article 1 Paragraph 1 states "Education is an effort made consciously and structured to create learning conditions and learning activities in such a way that students actively develop their abilities to have religious spiritual strength, self-mastery, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed for their respective individuals, communities, nations and countries".

Daryanto and Mulyo (2012: 9) suggest "Motivation is a process to activate motives for actions or actions to meet needs and achieve goals or conditions and readiness in a person that encourages his behavior to do something in achieving a certain goal". Another opinion is also expressed by Djaali (2012: 101) that "Motivation is a person's psychological and physiological state that encourages him to take certain actions so as to achieve goals (needs)". It can be concluded that motivation is a process of action / behavior of a person that arises in him so that he does actions that are useful to achieve the desired end. Someone who has a desire and goal for something, will be motivated to achieve it.

Learning motivation is an important aspect to determine students to be active in learning and able to achieve planned learning goals. Students' lack of motivation can affect the learning outcomes of the students themselves. Motivation does not only come from within (Internal) but also needs support from outside (External). Internal motivation is a desire or willingness that arises from a person's personality to take an action without pressure from any angle.

Meanwhile, external motivation is the desire or willingness that arises and is influenced by outsiders due to invitations, orders or coercion from outsiders to do certain things or learning activities.

In the world of education, it is important to have facilities and infrastructure as facilities for teaching and learning. Educational facilities are tools needed in the learning and teaching process, both moving and non-moving to achieve educational goals to run smoothly, structured, effectively and efficiently (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2009). One of the causes of the gap in education is that the infrastructure in a school is still limited and does not support learning in the classroom. Based on Permendiknas No. 24 of 2007, a minimum SMA/MA has facilities in the form of classrooms, teachers' rooms, laboratories, libraries, computer labs, language labs, meeting rooms, administrative offices, places of worship, counseling rooms, UKS, organization rooms, toilets, warehouses, and sports areas. The availability of complete infrastructure facilities can support smooth running and as one of the factors that generate learning motivation so that learning objectives can be achieved.

In reality, after observations related to the learning environment which involves infrastructure and learning motivation, there are still many grade XI students who do not utilize the existing infrastructure in the classroom. This is evidenced when there are empty hours and given several practicum assignments students prefer to play games, chat, and so on. It can be seen from the condition of these students, the researcher analyzes the effect of infrastructure facilities in the classroom on the level of learning motivation in students.

Related Work

Learning Motivation

According to Sardiman (2003: 75) in the book *Learning Variables*, the meaning of learning motivation is the overall driving force in the student's personality that generates learning activities and directs the learning process, to achieve the goals desired by the learning subject itself. According to Smittle (2003: 9) in the book *Learning Variables*, the meaning of motivation is a person's behavior which is basically determined by the desire to achieve goals. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (2002: 57) in the book *Learning Variables*, motivation is the desire to use all efforts (effort) to achieve maximum goals, which are determined by the ability of his efforts to meet his needs. The explanation of motivation above is interpreted as a person's efforts in carrying out learning activities to achieve the desired goals. Having motivation in learning can have a good impact on students to explore their interests and develop so as to achieve certain goals.

There are several functions affecting student learning motivation. According to Hamalik (2004: 161) in the book *Learning Variables*, the functions of learning motivation are 1) Encourage the emergence of behavior or action. Students are supported to carry out activities such as learning. 2) Motivation as a guide / direction, interpreted as an activity that leads to the goal to be achieved. 3) Motivation as a driver, means that it encourages behavior in a person, the amount of motivation given affects how quickly a goal is achieved. Judging from its function, learning motivation greatly affects student conditions, where providing motivation can have a big impact on learning outcomes and achieving learning goals.

In providing motivation, of course, there are several influencing factors. Delivered by Imron quoted from Siregar and Nara (2010: 53-54) there are 6 factors that affect learning motivation, among others: 1) Student ideals or aspirations, learning motivation arises when someone has big aspirations to realize them. 2) Student ability, a person's ability to complete certain tasks will provide its own satisfaction so that motivation will grow to continue to provide good results. 3) The condition of the student, motivation is influenced by the condition of the student where if the student has a good and healthy condition, it will foster high learning motivation, and vice versa if the student has an unhealthy condition, it will cause laziness to learn. 4) Environmental conditions that are safe, clean and comfortable can have a positive impact and generate motivation to learn. 5) Dynamic elements of learning / learning, the elements referred to here include teaching materials, main tools and learning support tools, learning atmosphere, learning methods and so on. 6) Teacher efforts in teaching, teachers have efforts or strategies in teaching.

Apart from the efforts made within students to increase learning motivation, there are also efforts that must be made by the teacher. Educators have a big role to play in increasing motivation in learning. So as educators need to know the characteristics of students who have different abilities. Sagala (2012: 153) in the book *Learning Variables* explains that there are 6 efforts that an educator must make to arouse student learning motivation, namely 1) Applying different teaching methods and media. The learning strategies and media used have an influence on learning motivation where the use of inappropriate methods and media can reduce student boredom. 2) Planning and selecting materials that are of interest and tailored to student needs. As a teacher, it is necessary to know and meet the learning needs of students, so that students will feel able to develop their interests and abilities to the maximum. 3) Provide intermediate goals,

final learning goals. Such as giving mid-semester exams, end-of-semester exams, quizzes, daily tests, portfolios that will be able to create learning motivation. 4) Provide opportunities for success. The ability of students is certainly different from others, therefore educators ask questions that are in accordance with their abilities. If the student is good we can give difficult questions and if the student is less good we can give moderate questions. 5) Creating a pleasant learning space. Growing the spirit of learning can be seen from the pleasant learning atmosphere. There is no reproach, but there is a warm class, a sense of family and mutual respect. 6) Healthy competition. Have a healthy learning competition without harming other students.

Infrastructure Facilities

Infrastructure facilities are an important aspect that must exist to support the learning process. Facilities in education are a set of equipment / furniture that is used directly to support activities or activities in learning. According to KBBI, facilities are an action that is used as a medium to achieve goals and objectives; can be in the form of tools or media. Another opinion by Osahon, 2001 (in the Journal of Office Management Education: 2018), facilities are equipment and equipment that are directly used to facilitate the learning and teaching process. From this explanation, it is concluded that the facility is a set of media or equipment that is used directly for learning and teaching activities.

Based on KBBI Infrastructure is everything that is the main support for the implementation of an activity. According to Suharno, 2008 that infrastructure can be interpreted as a service that indirectly supports the course of learning and teaching. From the above definition, the conclusion of infrastructure facilities is a component in the form of school facilities, media, equipment used during learning and teaching at school.

Infrastructure facilities have components including land, buildings, rooms, furniture, equipment, practical materials, teaching materials, sports facilities and the school environment according to learning media. These components must be present in a school to be able to support learning to the maximum. Adequate facilities and infrastructure are able to provide benefits for a school, namely being able to foster motivation to learn in class, being a source of learning, infrastructure can support teachers in organizing learning activities and complete infrastructure in the form of learning tools and materials can convey messages effectively and efficiently.

The Effect of Infrastructure Facilities on Learning Motivation

It is undeniable that facilities and infrastructure play an important role in learning success. Fulfillment of proper facilities and infrastructure encourages students to have enthusiasm for learning. Likewise, on the contrary, if a school has inadequate infrastructure, it will interfere with learning and reduce learning motivation. Learning that utilizes sarpras in schools can make it easier for students to capture the material taught and increase learning motivation. Interaction in learning becomes more alive because students directly carry out activities so that it allows students to explore their abilities.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that infrastructure facilities have a direct involvement with student learning motivation or it can be said that infrastructure facilities affect student motivation for maximum learning.

Relevant Research

The research carried out certainly cannot be separated from supporting sources that help researchers carry out this activity. Of the many sources of literature review found, there are several that provide the same description for student learning motivation. Researchers took sources from pre-existing journals and articles. The first research was conducted by Saniatu and Uep in 2018 which showed that infrastructure facilities have a strong relationship with motivation and are a decisive factor. The second research by Rasmuin and Fiana in 2019 was conducted with a t-test with the results of 8.672, significant at $0.000 < 0.05$ and concluded that there was a significant influence between infrastructure facilities and learning motivation. The third research by Ratna, Andi and Aji in 2019 which shows that learning facilities affect the motivation of grade V elementary school as evidenced by the rejection of H_0 and H_a where $r_{count} > r_{table}$ of $0.325 > 0.628$ with a significant level of 5%.

Research Method

Type of research

The research was conducted using quantitative methods. The use of this method aims to obtain information about the condition of infrastructure in the classroom and the influence on student motivation to learn.

Place of Research

The research location was carried out at SMK Negeri 2 Karanganyar class XI RPL (Software Engineering). The research was conducted when the researchers carried out PPL 1 Teacher Professional Program activities at the school.

Research Sample

The samples taken were 30 students in classes XI RA, XI RB and XI RC.

Data Collection Techniques and Research Instruments

Data collection methods are interviews and questionnaires. Students will receive a questionnaire containing questions given. This questionnaire is semi-closed where answers have been provided so that students just choose according to what they experience. The questionnaire is divided into 2 parts, namely a questionnaire to measure the infrastructure in the classroom and a questionnaire to measure learning motivation. While the interview was conducted with the head of the RPL (Software Engineering) expertise program at SMK Negeri 2 Karanganyar to see the condition of the infrastructure in the classroom and his views on learning motivation from class XI students.

The validity test uses the Product Moment formula and the reliability test uses the Cronbach Alpha formula (Suharsimi Arikunto 2015: 255).

Table 1. Correlation Coefficient

Interval	Level
0.00 – 0.19	Very Low
0.20 – 0.39	Low
0.40 – 0.59	Medium
0.60 – 0.79	Strong
0.80 – 1.00	Very Strong

Result and Discussion

Result

From the research that has been done, the results of interviews with teachers are obtained to find out the condition of infrastructure and student motivation during learning. The interview questions asked are in the table below:

Table 2. Interview Results of Pamong Teacher

No	Question	Result
1	How does the infrastructure in the classroom affect the learning motivation of class XI RPL?	The influence of infrastructure facilities in the classroom is a very important need to support learning. Great motivation is influenced by environmental conditions such as tools or media in the classroom and the use of learning / practical tools.
2	Do the facilities and infrastructure in the classroom meet learning needs?	The infrastructure in the classroom has met the needs of learning in the classroom. There is equipment that students can use in learning such as computers, LCD, internet, air conditioning and others.
3	What is the state of learning motivation of grade XI students?	The condition of student motivation towards learning is still lacking. This is caused by several factors where these factors can be from several aspects within themselves or aspects from outside.
4	What efforts do teachers make to foster student motivation in the classroom?	There are several efforts that teachers make, namely by providing an understanding of the importance of getting an education, the importance of obtaining knowledge for the future, providing an understanding of the benefits of science and information technology in real life.
5	What factors influence student enthusiasm when learning?	From the results of the observations carried out, there are several factors that influence students' enthusiasm when learning, including family, the surrounding environment, classroom conditions and learning models.

Furthermore, the questionnaire data was processed to determine the effect of infrastructure facilities on the learning motivation of class XI students, analyzed using the Product Moment correlation formula. Researchers took 30 samples of questionnaire data for infrastructure facilities while learning motivation data were taken 30 samples.

Table 3. Correlation of X and Y Values

SAMPEL	x	y	x ²	y ²	xy
R1	37	31	1369	961	1147
R2	31	39	961	1521	1209
R3	30	33	900	1089	990
R4	35	38	1225	1444	1330
R5	30	33	900	1089	990
R6	35	31	1225	961	1085
R7	30	34	900	1156	1020
R8	46	43	2116	1849	1978
R9	36	35	1296	1225	1260
R10	31	37	961	1369	1147
R11	35	41	1225	1681	1435
R12	39	39	1521	1521	1521
R13	41	41	1681	1681	1681
R14	42	45	1764	2025	1890
R15	40	40	1600	1600	1600
R16	30	30	900	900	900
R17	45	39	2025	1521	1755
R18	34	34	1156	1156	1156
R19	42	37	1764	1369	1554
R20	34	34	1156	1156	1156
R21	35	43	1225	1849	1505
R22	38	35	1444	1225	1330
R23	33	30	1089	900	990
R24	42	41	1764	1681	1722
R25	39	38	1521	1444	1482
R26	50	50	2500	2500	2500
R27	34	31	1156	961	1054
R28	44	43	1936	1849	1892
R29	50	40	2500	1600	2000
R30	39	39	1521	1521	1521
Jumlah	1127	1124	43301	42804	42800

After obtaining data in the form of variable X (infrastructure facilities) and variable Y (motivation), the researcher calculates the correlation between these variables to determine whether there is an influence or not using the

$$\text{formula: } r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{\{N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2\} \{N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{30.42800 - (1127)(1124)}{\sqrt{30.43301 - (1127)^2} \{30.42804 - (1124)^2\}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{1284000 - 1266748}{\sqrt{\{1299030 - 1270129\} \{1284120 - 1263376\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{17252}{\sqrt{\{28901\}\{20744\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{17252}{\sqrt{599522344}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{17252}{24485,145} = 0,70$$

Diagram 1. X and Y Gain Results

Diagram 2. X and Y Correlation Results

Discussion

After the calculation, the r_{count} result is 0.70. The data is correlated with the table on the r-product moment adjusted for a total of $N = 30$, by looking at the error rate of 5%, so that an r_{tabel} of 0.361 is obtained. Thus $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{tabel}}$ which is obtained at $0.70 > 0.361$, it is stated that H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected.

When viewed from the correlation table previously described, the r_{count} value which shows the existence of infrastructure facilities affects the learning motivation of class XI students with a range of 0.60 - 0.79 which is categorized as "strong". Further data was conveyed by the teacher during the interview that there are infrastructure facilities in the classroom that affect student learning motivation.

Furthermore, calculating the reliability between the infrastructure instrument and learning motivation using the Cronbach Alpha formula. Calculating the variance of each instrument, and doing the total of the instruments obtained results for infrastructure facilities 7.23 and learning motivation 6.39 with a total of 13.6. If done the overall total variance between the sarpras instrument and motivation is 57.1. To calculate the reliability of the instrument using the Cronbach alpha calculation, namely:

$$r_{11} = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum \sigma^2 b}{\sigma^2 t} \right)$$

$$r_{11} = \left(\frac{20}{20-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{13,6}{57,1} \right) = 0,80$$

The results of the manual calculation of the value on the instrument used are greater than r_{table} ($0.80 > 0.361$) which concluded that the instrument is reliable. For each questionnaire, the presentation of each questionnaire of infrastructure facilities and learning motivation is also produced, which shows 75.1% for sarpras and 74.9% for motivation. It means that the breakfast infrastructure in the classroom has an influence to increase student learning motivation while in class.

Conclusion

Teachers as educators have a role to pay attention to the motivation of their students while in class. There are several factors that influence the level of student motivation, including the availability of infrastructure in the classroom to support learning. After making various efforts to find out the relationship between facilities and infrastructure with learning motivation, the resulting research shows that there is a good influence between classroom infrastructure facilities on student learning motivation. This proof is seen from the results of the correlation test which obtained a value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely $0.748 > 0.361$ with a significance level of 5% with the participation of 30 respondents. In other words, school infrastructure facilities have an influence on the learning motivation of class XI students. Each instrument is tested for reliability which results in a value of $0.80 > 0.361$ which means reliable. While the percentage of each instrument gets 75.1% for infrastructure and 74.9% for motivation. It can be concluded that infrastructure facilities affect the learning motivation of grade XI RPL students at SMK Negeri 2 Karanganyar.

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